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A Case Report

**RELATION BETWEEN ABO BLOOD GROUPS AND
CHOLELITHIASIS AMONG POPULATION IN AL-MADINA,
SAUDI ARABIA, 2018: CASE-CONTROL STUDY.*****Ghassan Alsisi¹, Shireen Albouq², AlaaAlrehaili², Abdullah Almutairi³,
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Abstract:

Introduction: studies recently were talking about ABO blood groups and whether it's linked to some diseases or not. Cholelithiasis had a room between these studies too, but different studies have shown different results. However, there is no case-control study was done to confirm the relation rather than finding an association.

Methods: An observational analytical case-control study had been carried out in King Fahad Hospital, Al-Madina, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The study had been conducted through the year 2018. Both descriptive and inferential statistics had been conducted.

Results: Majority of the participants were female as 266 (63.2%) while 155 (36.8%) were males. Out of these numbers, 218 (51.8%) were aged 31 – 50 years old. Blood type O was the highest among participants with 194 (46.1%), followed by blood type A with 119 (28.3%), next was blood type B with 90 (21.4%) and with a relatively low number of blood type AB as 18 (04.3%). There was a significant relationship found in the age group and blood type group.

Conclusion: The findings of this study indicated that those patients in the middle age group with blood type O will likely to have cholelithiasis. Although more investigation is needed to support this claim, however, since the majority of our sample size was blood type O, we cannot generalize at this stage that blood group O is one of the major risk factors of cholelithiasis.

Keywords: Cholelithiasis, Gall Bladder, Gallstone, ABO, Blood group.

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INTRODUCTION:

A lot of studies recently were talking about ABO blood groups and whether it's linked to some diseases or not. Some have been shown a definite association with coronary heart diseases [1], duodenal ulcer [1], gastric cancer [1], pancreatic cancer [1]. Cholelithiasis had a room between these studies too, but different studies have shown different results. Blood group (A) has the higher risk of cholelithiasis according to some studies [1,2,3]. Others [1,2] considered blood group (AB) to be the risk factor. While a study [1] showed that blood group (O) is the risk, On the other hand, a study [1] proved the lack of significant association between the blood groups and risk of having cholelithiasis. However, there is no case-control study was done to confirm the relation rather than finding an association. So, we are aiming in this study to determine if there is a significant relation in our population in Al-Madina between the ABO blood groups and risk of cholelithiasis.

MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY:

An observational analytical case-control study will be carried out in King Fahad Hospital, Al-Madina, Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. The study will be conducted through the year 2018. The case group (220 cases) were both male and female regardless the age who were diagnosed as a case of gallstone. All cases who have another risk disease for gallstone were excluded such as alcoholic, blood diseases, pancreatic diseases, Crohn's disease, and patients post sleeve. Obesity was considered by measuring the body mass index (BMI). Selected cases had +ve US finding and confirmed by operative notes of cholecystectomy with known blood group types. (201 cases) Control group were patients who diagnosed as morbid obese although they were not risk-free (obesity), it was the only group which we were able to reach their US findings and blood types since they are planned for bariatric surgery. All the data for this study were collected from

hospital system and medical records via semi-structured form.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS:

Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) version 20 had been used to conduct all statistical analyses for this project. Both descriptive and inferential statistics such as relationship and regression tables had been conducted. A p-value cut off point of 0.05 at 95% CI used to determine statistical significance. The analyses measure the relationship between socio-demographic and other related variables in the survey by using chi-square test. Regression analysis had been conducted as well where Odds ratio and 95% CI were also being reported for the risk factor of the dependent variables versus socio-demographic characteristics participants. Data were tabulated by using Microsoft office — Excel sheet, entered and analyzed by using SPSS, version 20.0. Ethical Committee approval was obtained before starting the study.

RESULTS:

(Table 1) presented the description of the socio-demographic characteristics of 421 participants. Majority of the participants were female as 266 (63.2%) while 155 (36.8%) were males. Out of these numbers, 218 (51.8%) were aged 31 – 50 years old, 114 (27.1%) were 16 – 30 years old and 89 (21.1%) were more than 50 years old. Blood type O was the highest among participants with 194 (46.1%), followed by blood type A with 119 (28.3%), next was blood type B with 90 (21.4%) and with a relatively low number of blood type AB as 18 (04.3%). RH positive was predominantly higher with 390 (92.6%) and only 31 (07.4%) were RH negative. More participants were obese with 247 (58.7%), with 118 (28.0%) were overweight and 56 (13.3%) had normal BMI. Regarding cholelithiasis group, case group was slightly higher than the control group as 220 (52.3%) and 201 (47.7%) respectively.

Table 1: Description of socio demographic variables

Study Variables	N (%) (n = 421)
Gender	
• Male	155 (36.8%)
• Female	266 (63.2%)
Age group in years	
• 16 – 30 years old	114 (27.1%)
• 31 – 50 years old	218 (51.8%)
• >50 years old	89 (21.1%)
Blood group	
• A	119 (28.3%)
• AB	18 (04.3%)
• B	90 (21.4%)
• O	194 (46.1%)
RH	
• Negative	31 (07.4%)
• Positive	390 (92.6%)
Classification of BMI	
• Normal	56 (13.3%)
• Overweight	118 (28.0%)
• Obese	247 (58.7%)
Cholelithiasis group	
• Control	201 (47.7%)
• Case	220 (52.3%)

We used chi-square test at (**Table 2**) to measure the relationship between socio-demographic variables with p-values which signifies whether the relationship is statistically significant. We used $p \leq 0.05$ as the level of significance for all statistical tests. Females were predominantly higher on both groups compared to males, but their relationship found to be negative (0.157). Age group 31 – 50 years old were higher on both case and control groups in comparison to other age categories, the analysis revealed that age shows significant relationship ($p < 0.001$). Blood type O was superior on both group of cholelithiasis in contrast to other blood type groups and its p-values show a significant difference ($p = 0.038$). RH positive was far off better to both group of cholelithiasis compared to RH negative, however,

0.411). Regarding BMI group, all participants in control group were obese while overweight was higher in case group. It was revealed that BMI has a strong relationship with the group of cholelithiasis ($p = 0.001$).

(**Table 3**) shows the regression analysis predicting case versus control from the socio-demographic characteristics of participants. Socio-demographic variables included in the model such as gender, age group in years, blood group and RH group. According to the analysis it shows, age group in years 16 – 30 years old (OR 0.207, $p < 0.001$) and 31 – 50 years old (OR 0.405, $p = 0.001$) and blood group O (OR 1.704, $p = 0.043$) were all statistically significant. Other variables included in the model shows not statistically significant.

Table 2: Relationship between the two group of Cholelithiasis and socio-demographic characteristics (n = 421)

Characteristics	Control (n = 201) N (%)	Case (n = 220) N (%)	P-value §
Gender			
• Male	81 (40.3%)	74 (33.6%)	0.157
• Female	120 (59.7%)	146 (66.4%)	
Age group in years			
• 16 – 30 years old	73 (36.3%)	41 (18.6%)	<0.001 **
• 31 – 50 years old	104 (51.7%)	114 (51.8%)	
• >50 years old	24 (11.9%)	65 (29.5%)	
Blood group			
• A	64 (31.8%)	55 (25.0%)	0.038 **
• AB	11 (05.5%)	07 (03.2%)	
• B	32 (15.9%)	58 (26.4%)	
• O	94 (46.8%)	100 (45.5%)	
RH			
• Negative	17 (08.5%)	14 (06.4%)	0.411
• Positive	184 (91.5%)	206 (93.6%)	
Classification of BMI			
• Normal	0	56 (25.5%)	<0.001 **
• Overweight	0	118 (53.6%)	
• Obese	201 (100%)	46 (20.9%)	

RH – Rhesus; BMI – Body Mass Index. §P-value has been calculated using Chi-square test. **Significant at $p \leq 0.05$ level.

its relationship to cholelithiasis was negative ($p =$

Table 3: Regression analysis to predict case vs control on socio demographic characteristics of participants ^(n = 421)

Characteristics	Odds Ratio	95% CI	P-value [§]
Gender			
• Male	Ref		
• Female	0.751	0.505 – 1.117	0.157
Age group in years			
• 16 – 30 years old	Ref		
• 31 – 50 years old	0.207	0.113 – 0.380	<0.001 **
• >50 years old	0.405	0.236 – 0.693	0.001 **
Blood group			
• A	Ref		
• AB	0.808	0.511 – 1.276	0.360
• B	0.598	0.223 – 1.608	0.308
• O	1.704	1.018 – 2.852	0.043 **
RH			
• Negative	0.736	0.353 – 1.534	0.413
• Positive	Ref		

CI – Confidence Interval; RH – Rhesus.

DISCUSSION:

Several studies with the same perspective had been published online but few of them correlated blood group to cholelithiasis. In our study, we found a positive correlation between blood group and gallbladder disease. Our outcome also shows the majority of the females were suffering from the disease and more than a half of the middle age patients in the blood group O were likely to have cholelithiasis. We found also a significant relationship between gender, age group in years and classification of BMI however, it shows a negative relationship on gender and Rh. In India, the incidence of cholecystitis was high in females. [10,1,12] They also reported that blood type of O was the highest incidence of the disease among the other blood groups. These study findings were incongruent with our study outcome where we also exhibited the same prevalence of blood type group and with comparable result in gender. Although one of the mentioned studies was about cholecystitis and its predilection to blood group which somewhat different subject in nature nonetheless, this disease was in the same region and emanated in the same organ. A group of researchers from Taiwan investigated age as the risk factor of gallstone disease (GSD). [1] With only 10.7% had been positively identified in the studied group, their findings show age, high body mass index, diabetes mellitus, and glucose intolerance were the risk factors for developing GSD however they failed to correlate blood group into GSD. Generally, we can say that our project outcome was

similar in nature. Although we found a negative association on some of the important variables, we can still assert that the key aim of our study had been achieved. Interestingly in Germany, the prevalence of gallstone was high in blood group AB. [8] However, their study outcome revealed that no significant relationship between each variable. Moreover, in Austria, they proved that cholelithiasis was strongly correlated with the blood type group. [1] While in Italy, they failed to prove the significant difference between ABO and cholelithiasis. [1] Several projects in the same context but distinctive in the outcome. This suggests that the phenomenon of this study discipline was not yet fully uncovered. This is due to inconsistencies of study findings most especially in correlating ABO to gallbladder disease.

CONCLUSION:

The findings of this study indicated that those patients in the middle age group with blood type O will likely to have cholelithiasis. Although more investigations are needed to support this claim, however, since the majority of our sample size were blood type O, we cannot generalize at this stage that blood group O is one of the major risk factors of cholelithiasis. Consideration of new research in the same context is recommended involving balance proportion of blood group to eliminate biased and obtain a better scenario.

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